

An Empirical Study on the Relationship Between FDI and Migration in Romania

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Abstract

Foreign capital flows play a key role both in the beneficiary and the source country due to the positive externalities they generate on economic growth and labor market indicators, materialized into tangible and intangible assets. This paper aims to analyze the relationship between FDI inflows in Romania and the number of immigrants, based on data over the period 1991-2010. The results of the VAR model and from the estimated equation highlight a positive and intense correlation between FDI and GDP, meanwhile the relationship between inward FDI in Romania and the number of immigrants is relatively strong, but negative.

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Keywords: FDI inflows, immigrants, labor market, GDP, VAR

1. Introduction

The global economy is notably influenced by the economic and financial globalization, which often is correlated with an “increase in the number of people with the desire and capacity to move to other places” (Annan, 2006). The globalization process is usually interpreted by a strong increase of the interrelationships between worldwide economies through the integration of goods, services, labor and capital on the international markets, generating substantial gains for the countries which decided to open their borders to trade, foreign capital flows and international migration, because “migrations are not isolated phenomena: movements of commodities and capital almost always cause movements of people” (Castles, Miller, 2003: p. 4).

Free movements of capitals (FDI) and international labor migration stimulate the economic development of the recipient country, being in the same time dependent on the complex economic, institutional and policy variables (Tasy, Tsai, 2009). Romania passed through an intensive and extended transition process, along with other Central and Eastern European countries, which encouraged national development and important progresses in achieving a higher rate of economic growth, as part of the globalization phenomenon. The progresses made by Romania were caused by the policies and strategies carried out to increase the national attractiveness reflected in an ascending trend of the volume of foreign direct investments. On the other side, even if Romania obtained significant progresses in the economy, the steps made are small and a part of the population left the country, causing an increase of the migration process, due to several reasons: family reunification, ethnic migration, business migration, international student mobility as a stimulation of the brain drain.

The paper aims to study for Romania the relationship between FDI and migration, being structured in the following sections: second part of the paper presents the theoretical aspects regarding the connection between FDI and migration, the third part highlights the data and methodology used to analyse the correlation among the selected variables, in the fourth section the results will be presented and discussed, meanwhile the last part of the paper will emphasize the most important conclusions of the study.

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2. Theoretical aspects regarding the relationship between FDI and migration

The literature discussing the relationship between FDI and migration highlights the existing debates on the aspect through the controversial results, most of them attempted to investigate the impact on the economy and to identify the fundamental channels. Although the number of the studies focusing on the correlation between FDI and migration is increasing, the topic is still under-investigated. Migration is able to enhance economic development of the beneficiary country through simplifying the access to information, telecommunication systems and information transformation, generating a positive and favorable impact on reducing the barriers to people mobility. FDI impact on migration is materialized in reducing the pressure on labor demand through the positive effects on development, by stimulating economic growth and sustaining employment creation.

FDI introduce into the host country tangible and intangible assets and cause a positive influence on migration by improving the internal labor market by creating new job opportunities, reducing the tendency of migration for low income workers (Tsay, Tsai, 2003), especially in middle and upper – income countries and transition economies, being necessary a threshold level of economic development (UNCTAD, 2009; UN, 1996).

The model developed by Barry (2002) reveals the dependence of peripheral economies on FDI flows which stimulate the development of the modern sectors where raising return prevail. Through the perspective of the source country, Ivelvs and De Mello (2008) examined the interrelations between pattern of migration, trade policy and foreign capital flows using a general equilibrium model. They also highlighted the complementarities between FDI and migration based on a cross – sectional analysis for 103 countries covering the period 1990-2000. A significant volume of the past theoretical and empirical studies are focused on Diaspora and human capital effects due to the correlation between FDI, trade and migration. Schiff (2007) recognizes the complex character of the relationship between FDI, trade and migration and the difficulty to draw adequate policy recommendations for the countries involved. Using emigration data over 1990 – 2000, Docquier and Marfouk (2006) demonstrated the upward trend recorded by the north – south migration, thus, in other paper, Docquier, Lohest and Marfouk (2007) concentrated on the main channels through which emigration influences the welfare of the home country.

FDI activities face larger information asymmetries than international trade transactions and direct investments usually require long – term focus and interactions with various groups of economic agents as suppliers, workers and consumers. Javorcik, et. al.(2010) had a strong contribution to the existing literature, by considering an endogeneity problem which was ignored in previous studies and showed that US FDI abroad is strongly correlated with the presence of educated migrants.

FDI have a key role in host country economy by introducing capital, modern technology and equipments stimulating economic growth and creating employment opportunities and reducing the willingness to migrate. Educated and high – skilled migration, especially from developing countries to the developed ones often has an adverse effect on home country economy, because the workers migration is a channel for information transfer across borders. Bhattacharya and Groznic (2008) and Buch et. al. (2006) found a positive correlation between the two variables, meanwhile Kugler and Rapaport (2007) showed, based on a panel of 55 countries that migration of workers with primary and tertiary education is associated with an increase in future US FDI. Federici and Giannetti (2008) and Ivelvs (2005) were among the ones who discovered a link between FDI and migration.

Gheasi, et. al. (2011) bring their contribution to the theoretical and empirical literature by analyzing the mechanisms through which foreign capital flows can influence the determinants of migration and the

appropriate policies to manage this phenomena. FDI enhance internal labor demand both for skilled and unskilled workers by boosting the degree of openness for developing countries and causing a reduction of costs

of migration. Foreign capital inflows stimulate human capital formation and improve labour market conditions by eliminating the gap between developed and developing countries.

Overman and Puga (2002) appreciate that international trade and foreign capital inflows reinforce the existing pattern of unemployment and according to previous studies, the impact of trade expansion on employment is significant in countries which are large FDI beneficiaries, but has a slow influence on job creation in countries the reduce the volume of FDI. Early empirical analysis considered that income gaps and unemployment were the key drivers of migration, although the economic theory does not provide a full satisfactory model for studying the causes and effects of migration, meanwhile the macroeconomic neoclassical theory explains migration through a mismatch in labor supply and demand and wages differences by contrast to microeconomic theory which focuses on cost – benefit deliberation. Kim (2006) developed a VECM to study the interactions between aggregate immigration, inbound FDI and imports, using annual US data from 1969 – 2000, showing that variance decomposition identifies a causal correlation among variables and an impulse response function emphasizing their response with respect to each variable. He proved that immigration generates imports and inbound FDI which appear to be substitutes, meanwhile immigrants and inbound FDI are complements.

The relationship between FDI and migration operates through labor market, foreign capitals being able to create more demand for labor and higher employment for unskilled workers, which can be translated into lower migration incentives. The effects in the national economy vary with the country characteristics, migration trajectories, history or tradition (Xenogiani, 2006).

3. Data and methodology

The data used are selected form the UNCTAD database and the National Institute of Statistics over the period 1991 – 2011. The information for all the variables was available only since 1991 and this is the main reason why we have chosen this period. Second, since 1991 Romania suffered the major changes in the economy and led to the most important transformations in the dynamic of macroeconomic variables.

In the analysis were included the volume of foreign direct inflows, the unemployment rate, the logarithm of the GDP and the number of the immigrants for the chosen period. The relationship between FDI and the migration process will we demonstrated based on a VAR model which will hep us identify the estimation equation to be tested. In the first step of the analysis , the variables will be tested to check their stationarity and then the VAR model will be carried out.

4. Results and discussion

First, for each variable included in the analysis we determined the descriptive statistics, which results are presented in the table below, showing according to the that they are normally distributed.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

Indicators	FDI INFLOWS	IMMIGRANTS	LGDP	UNEMPLOYMENT
Mean	3347.950	6228.050	10.75049	7.230000
Median	1186.500	6591.000	11.49000	6.950000
Std. Dev.	4155.497	3817.375	2.350607	1.738451
Skewness	1.350401	-0.028294	-0.877397	0.114180
Kurtosis	3.596152	1.435893	2.689266	3.903947
Jarque-Bera	6.374775	2.041360	2.646548	0.724391
Probability	0.041280	0.360350	0.266262	0.696146

The implementation of the VAR model involves the determination of the stationarity of those four variables selected, through carrying out the Augmented Dickey – Fuller test, which will highlight the level of

integration for each of them. The results of the Augmented Dickey – Fuller test are provided in the following table.

Table 2. Augmented Dickey – Fuller test results

Null Hypothesis: FDI_inflows has a unit root			
unemployment has a unit root			
lgdp has a unit root			
immigrants has a unit root			
Augmented Dickey Fuller test statistic	Critical values	t-statistic	Probability*
FDI_inflows	-3.052169	-4.796509	0.0017
Unemployment	-3.052169	-5.232906	0.0007
Lgdp	-3.065585	-5.398475	0.0006
Immigrants	-3.065585	-3.224974	0.0373

(note: values are significant at a 5 % level)

The results regarding the ADF test show that, according to the t-statistic values and their associated probability these are have I(0) of integration, meaning that they are integrated at level. This will allow us to apply the VAR methodology and the identification of the equation to be estimated through Least Square method.

$$FDI_INFLOWS = C(1)*FDI_INFLOWS(-1) + C(2)*LGDP(-1) + C(3)*UNEMPLOYMENT(-1) + C(4)*IMMIGRANTS(-1) + C(5) \tag{1}$$

Least Square method showed that FDI inflows have a strong and positive influence on the value and the dynamic of the national GDP. Similar to previous studies, this paper succeeded to emphasize the important contribution foreign capital inflows have on the national economic development, through their major consequences in the internal business environment and economy (transfer of technology, transfer of skills and other capabilities, managerial and organizational abilities).

Table 3. Least Square method – estimation results

Dependent Variable: FDI_INFLOWS				
Method: Least Squares				
Sample (adjusted): 1991 2011				
Included observations: 19 after adjustments				
FDI_INFLOWS = C(1)*FDI_INFLOWS(-1) + C(2)*LGDP(-1) + C(3)*UNEMPLOYMENT(-1) + C(4)*IMMIGRANTS(-1) + C(5)				
	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C(1)	0.517328	0.198903	2.600908	0.0209
C(2)	963.9881	431.4538	2.234279	0.0423
C(3)	-305.2697	381.2519	-0.800703	0.4367
C(4)	-0.456438	0.220689	-2.068236	0.0576
C(5)	-3506.714	4105.695	-0.854110	0.4074
R-squared	0.712692	Mean dependent var		3522.053
Adjusted R-squared	0.630604	S.D. dependent var		4193.755
S.E. of regression	2548.880	Akaike info criterion		18.74563
Sum squared resid	90955074	Schwarz criterion		18.99417
Log likelihood	-173.0835	Hannan-Quinn criter.		18.78769
F-statistic	8.682033	Durbin-Watson stat		2.233792
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000968			

The results showed that, at a 10 % level of significance, there is a strong negative and indirect relationship between FDI inflows in Romania and the dynamic of the immigrants, because the C(4) coefficient has a negative associated value of -0.456438. The foreign direct investment inflows ability to create new job opportunities in the beneficiary economy is reflected in an ascending trend of the economic development of the national economy, through an increase of the GDP growth rate in Romania.

However, the expansion of foreign multinational and their businesses in the Romanian economy is leading to a raise of the new jobs which is reflected into a decrease of the volume of the immigrants, because people are often attracted by more developed countries which allow them to gain more. Besides that, the immigrants are usually strongly influenced by more reasons, including foreign studies into other developed countries, by the willing to have an improved standard of life.

The model is very good because R-square is 71.26 % which is higher than 60%, the probability of F-statistic is 0.000968 showing that the independent variables are significant in explaining the variation of the dependent variable. The study of the residuals showed that they are normally distributed, are homoscedastic and are not serial correlated.

5. Concluding remarks

The relationship between FDI and migration was intensively debated in the theoretical and empirical literature and still offers controversial results. FDI inflows are expected to generate positive externalities in the host country economy and stimulate its development through the impact on national GDP and by transferring both tangible and intangible assets. The connection between FDI and migration flows must be analyzed in correlation to other macroeconomic variables, such as unemployment, GDP, because FDI are recognized for their influence on boosting economic growth and enhancing job occupancy which will have a favorable impact on reducing the unemployment rate and in the same time will reduce the number of the immigrants.

The analysis carried out in this study, for Romania, showed that FDI are strongly and positively correlated to the GDP, but also there is an intense and negative relationship between FDI inflows and the number of immigrants. To increase the role played by foreign capital flows in the national economy, the policy makers should focus to create and develop national strategies to increase national attractiveness for foreign investors and the effects they generate in the economy will be more intense.

The favorable externalities generated by the foreign direct investment inflows in Romania, reflected in a strong increase of the national GDP will stimulate the development of the business environment. On the other side, the positive impact enhances the expansion of the strategies which will improve the performance and the efficiency of all the economic business areas. The most important effect regarding the occupancy rate reflects an important decrease of the unemployment rate due to the new jobs created, the population will be less attracted to migration, meanwhile the number immigrants will decrease significantly.

Further analysis will be developed by including other Central Eastern European countries, whose results will allow a comparative study between the selected countries regarding their level of development, the volume of foreign direct investments attracted and the migration process. On the other side, a more expanded study will be focused on developed and emerging economies, which will lead us to draw important conclusions about their macroeconomic performances.

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